

Deliverable 0.2.1

Workpackage 0

JIP COVRIN

Responsible Partner: WBVR

Contributing partners: UoS (P23), IZSAM (P28), WBVR (P31), SVA (P41)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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COVRIN COMMUNICATION REPORT 1.

Introduction

Communication activities on the COVRIN project activities and project results are to be described in annual reports and in the COVRIN final report. These will include communications about results to the scientific community, to the stakeholders as well as the general public.

COVRIN Communication activities M36-M48

Communication activities in the first half year of the COVRIN project were started with internal communications within the EJP One Health network. The coordinator and the deputy coordinator presented the COVRIN proposal and the COVRIN work plan several times for the OHEJP project management team (PMT). Thereafter the COVRIN work plan was presented to the Project Owner Committee (POC), the scientific steering board (SSB), the external scientific advisory board (ESAB) and the Stakeholder Committee (SC). These presentations were shared via several social media platforms and also made available for the network partners via the OHEJP website.

Towards the end of the first project year, as more and more research outcomes and integration results and networking results became available, these outcomes were presented in a COVRIN presentation at the PMT, the POC, the SSB and the SC again. Such presentations were well received and like the earlier presentation these were also shared via social media and the EJPOH website.

Since there was not a communication officer appointed within the COVRIN project, most communication work was done by the COVRIN coordinator and the deputy. COVRIN communication activities were supported by the EJP communication team and by several of the partner communication officers. Both the team and the individual officers have repeatedly advertised the COVRIN project results via social media. COVRIN stakeholders were also updated by circulating an executive summary of the 12M report of the project. COVRIN research outcomes were also presented during several scientist network meetings and conferences. This included the STAR-IDAZ, a PREZODE program meeting and the European Society of Veterinary Virology meeting. COVRIN also connected with the UK International Coronavirus network. During one of the meetings of this network the COVRIN project was presented and COVRIN supports the UK CoVnet as an advisor and by helping to organize network meetings.

Conclusions COVRIN Communication activities M36-M48

COVRIN communication activities during the first year of the project consisted of a number of internal and external presentations about the project workplan and the project outcomes. This included presentations for OHEJP internal bodies and also project funders and stakeholders. Overall, COVRIN presentations were well received.